

West Messa Metal Mapper Data Inversion and Classification

Irma Shamatava^(1,2)

⁽¹⁾ White River Technologies, Inc, Lebanon, NH, 03756
E-mail: Shamatava@whiterivertech.com

Benjamin Barrowes⁽³⁾

⁽³⁾ USA-ARMY CRREL, Hanover, NH, 03755
E-mail: Benjamin.E.Barrowes@erdc.dren.mil

John Sigman⁽²⁾, Fridon Shubitidze^(1,2)

⁽²⁾ Dartmouth College, Hanover, NH, 03755
E-mail: Fridon.Shubitidze@dartmouth.edu

Abstract—In this paper, West Messa UXO classification results are presented for cued data collected by the Metal mapper sensor. Data sets are inverted using advanced forward EMI model called the orthonormalized volume magnetic source (ONVMS) model. All data are inverted as single, two and three sources. For each inversion, targets intrinsic parameters are extracted and used in a library matching technique. Anomalies are classified as targets of interest (TOI) and clutter.

Index Terms—Live UXO sites, Metal Mapper, sensors, MPV, electromagnetic induction, UXO, classification, discrimination, ONVMS.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the Environmental Security Technology Certification Program (ESTCP) launched a series of blind tests for advanced EMI sensors at increasingly challenging and complex live sites [1] to demonstrate the state of the art in EMI detection technologies and UXO discrimination and classification algorithms. In this paper we demonstrate advanced EMI models classification performance West Mesa site that is contaminated with a wide mixture of munitions buried at deferent depths. Our team processed Metal mapper cued data using the suite of advanced EMI discrimination techniques that we have developed in recent years with support from ESTCP and the Strategic Environmental Research and Development Program (SERDP). Our set of tools for modeling, inversion, and classification combine: 1) a joint-diagonalization (JD) algorithm that estimates the number of potential targets generating an anomaly directly from the measured data without need for inversion [2]; 2) the orthonormalized volume magnetic source (ONVMS) model [3] which locates targets, represents their EMI responses, and extracts their intrinsic feature vectors (in particular, their time-dependent total ONVMS amplitudes) [4] and 3) a Gaussian mixture algorithm that uses these extracted discrimination features to classify the corresponding buried objects as TOI or clutter [4]. Initially the data are inverted using a combination of ONVMS and the differential evolution (DE) optimization algorithm [5] to determine the subsurface targets' locations

and orientations; this allows the robust determination of their relevant intrinsic parameters, which in turn are classified by a mixture of clustering and library-matching techniques.

During the inversion stage, the total ONVMS is determined as a function of time for each anomaly. The ONVMS model is a further extension of the NSMS model (and hence of the dipole model) that builds on the assumption that the superposition of EMI responses of a collection of buried objects interrogated by a sensor can be represented as though it originated from a set of magnetic dipoles distributed over a volume. Since all actual radiating sources are located within the scatterers, rather than in the soil or air, the spatial distribution of these fictitious dipoles indicates the locations and orientations of any targets present inside the computational volume.

II. METAL MAPPER-SYSTEM

The Metal Mapper (MM) is an advanced EMI system for UXO detection and discrimination developed primarily by G&G Sciences and commercialized by Geometrics. The system has three mutually orthogonal transmitter rectangular loops. It is able to illuminate a target with primary fields from three independent directions from a single spatial field point. The 1 m × 1 m Z transmitter loop is located at ground level. The Y transmitter loop, also 1 m × 1 m, is centered 56 cm above the Z loop, as is the 0.98 m × 0.98 m X transmitter (Figure 1). The targets are illuminated from different directions depending on the geometry between a particular transmitting loop and the target. The system has seven 10-cm-side receiver cubes placed at seven unique spatial points on the plane of the Z transmitter loop. The receivers measure the vector $d\mathbf{B}/dt$ at each of the seven points, thus providing 63 independent readings of the transient secondary magnetic field for each instrument location. The positions of the receiver cubes' centers with respect to the Z transmitter loop (whose center we consider as the local origin of coordinates for the system) are given in [6].

Figure 1: The MetalMapper during SLO site deployment (left) and its schematic diagram (right).

The MM transmitters are modeled as infinitely thin rectangular wires. The primary magnetic induction produced at any observation point \mathbf{r} by the T -th loop is determined simply from the Biot-Savart law,

$$\mathbf{B}_T(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{Tx}} \frac{I_T [\Delta \ell_{T,i} \times \mathbf{R}_{T,i}]}{R_{T,i}^3}, \quad T = 1, 2, 3, \quad (1)$$

where, $\mathbf{R}_{T,i} = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'_{T,i}|$, $\mathbf{r}'_{T,i}$ is the location of the i -th current element, and $\Delta \ell_{j,i}$ is the tangential length vector for the i -th subsection of the loop. In what follows, and unless we note otherwise, we divide each transmitter coil into $N_{Tx} = 40$ subsections whenever we calculate the primary magnetic induction using Eq. (1).

The MM receiver assembly consists of seven cube sensors. Each of these measures along three orthogonal directions the induced voltages that, from Faraday's law, correspond to the negative of the time derivative of the secondary magnetic flux through the area spanned by the different coils. The induced voltage in the R -th sensor along the α -th direction, where $R = 0, \dots, 6$ and $\alpha = z, y, x$, is computed using

$$V_R^\alpha = - \int_{S_R^\alpha} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \cdot d\mathbf{s}_R^\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{Rx}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{r}_{i,R}^\alpha - \mathbf{r}_o)}{\partial t} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{n}}_\alpha \Delta s_{i,R}^\alpha, \quad (2)$$

where s_R^α is the area of the relevant coil (all of which are $10 \text{ cm} \times 10 \text{ cm}$ squares in Metal Mapper) and $\tilde{\mathbf{n}}_\alpha$ is the unit vector perpendicular to it, $\Delta s_{i,R}^\alpha$ and $\mathbf{r}_{i,R}^\alpha$ are respectively the i -th sub-area and vector location point on s_R^α , $\mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{r}_{i,R}^\alpha) = \mu_0 \mathbf{H}_i(\mathbf{r}_{i,R}^\alpha)$ is the magnetic induction (proportional to the magnetic field $\mathbf{H}_i(\mathbf{r}_{i,R}^\alpha)$) produced at $\mathbf{r}_{i,R}^\alpha$ by a source placed at \mathbf{r}_o . Within the ONVMS model, $\mathbf{H}_i(\mathbf{r}_{i,R}^\alpha)$ is calculated using equation (3). In what follows we always divide s_R^α into $N_{Rx} = 4$ sub-areas.

Figure 2. Inverted effective ONVMS for AN M30 Bomb. Test stand data, the target is oriented 45 degrees at 86 cm depth. The red lines are total ONVMS for a library AN M30 Bomb, and green, blue and black lines are effective primary, secondary and tertiary effective polarizabilities for the test AN M30 target respectively.

III. ONVMS

The ONVMS model can be considered as a generalized volume dipole model, and in fact contains the point dipole model as a limiting case. It is based on the assumption that a collection of scatterers can be replaced with a set of magnetic dipole sources, distributed over a volume, that mimic the eddy currents and magnetic response that are induced on the targets by the sensor and that in turn establish the secondary field. The physical induced dipoles and currents are distributed inside the objects in question, and thus the spatial distribution of the dipole sources (their amplitudes scaled by the primary field) traces a map of “response activity” with a clustering pattern that reveals the locations and orientations of the targets present within. The scattered magnetic field at any point outside a target can be represented using orthonormalized functions as

$$\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_o} \bar{\bar{\psi}}_i(\mathbf{R}_i) \cdot \mathbf{b}_i, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_i = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i^v$, $\bar{\bar{\psi}}_i(\mathbf{r})$ is an orthonormalized function, and \mathbf{b}_i is an expansion coefficient. As a first step, the orthonormal functions $\bar{\bar{\psi}}_i$ are constructed as Gram-Schmidt orthonormalized linear combinations of Green functions; the linear independence of Green dyadics then allows one to compute the amplitudes $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{M}}}_i(p)$ of the polarizability tensor elements without solving a linear system of equations [3].

Figure 3. Inverted effective ONVMS for AN M30 Bomb. Test stand data, the target is (**top**) oriented 45 degrees at 150 cm depth, and (**bottom**) oriented vertically 210 cm depth. The red lines are total ONVMS for a library AN M30 Bomb, and green, blue and black lines are effective primary, secondary and tertiary effective polarizabilities for the test AN M30 target respectively.

The ONVMS technique is readily applicable to both single- and multi-object data. Among its great advantages are 1) that it takes into account mutual couplings between different parts of a given target and 2) that it avoids matrix singularity problems in multi-object scenarios

IV. RESULTS

One of the potential targets of interest at West Mesa site is AN M30 Bomb, which is ~ 36 inch in length, 11 inch in diameter and weighs 100 pounds. These bombs are found at different depth and orientations anywhere from the surface to

two meters depth. Thus, one of the challenging problems for this site is to detect and discriminate reliable low signal to noise targets, i.e. classify deep AN M30 bombs accurately. To understand the metal mapper data detection and discrimination complexity, first test-stand data were collected by Environmental and Munitions Center of Expertise, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, personnel. We used these data sets and inverted targets classification parameters. The inverted parameters are shown on Figure 2 and Figure 3. These classification features matches very well to an expected library parameters, indicating that classification features can be extracted accurately for as shallow as well as deep targets. Thus the ONVMS technique is able to classify deep and challenging targets.

V. CONCLUSIONS

ONVMS technique was applied to AN M30 Bob metal mapper data test-stand data sets. The inverted parameters are analyzed from classification point of view. The studies have shown that our models are applicable as for shallow targets detection and classification, as well as they provide very accurate classification features for deep targets. The data from live West Mesa UXO site are inverted and the classification results will be presented during presentation.

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